

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

POSSIBLE INTERACTION OF THE SECURITY SYSTEMS DEVELOPMENT BUSINESS MODEL WITH THE ORGANIZATION'S VULNERABILITY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

The use of the competences of scientific organizations for the development of security systems for various objects, including critical infrastructure, is often associated with the development of a purpose-specific business model. The structuring of such a business model is also related to the assessment of the vulnerability of the objects for which the security systems will be developed. This affects the structure of the elements of the business model, as well as the relationships with the business models of other organizations with which key partnerships need to be established. The presentation of some regularities in the development of a business model of a scientific organization developing security systems and the impact of the vulnerability of the security object on the elements of the business model is the basis of this paper.

Keywords: business model, vulnerability analysis, security systems

Organizational strategy and competitiveness are based on the application of an appropriate business model (BM) and are based on an analysis of the organization's components, taking into account the assets created, the resources used, the plans developed and the competencies established, including the security systems development.

The development of security systems often falls within the scope of activity of scientific organizations, and the pragmatic solution for using their competences is the creation of a method for the development of the BM of the scientific organization, which may include, but not only: analysis of the significance of the product; a visual presentation of the product, including an illustration of its system of operation, and a competitive analysis of the product, including a search for changes and innovations.

At the same time, the use of BM by scientific organizations to develop security systems is closely related to the management of the vulnerability of the organization for which this system will be built, in this case critical infrastructure (CI). The life cycle of vulnerabilities management allows CI to improve the state of security through a more strategic approach aimed at managing vulnerabilities, namely, instead of responding to existing and new vulnerabilities when occurring, gaps are actively sought in organizational systems for the purpose to identify the most critical vulnerabilities and the introduction of defenses before the threat affects. This helps to properly determine the characteristics of the Security System, which is related to the application of a suitable BM of scientific organization.

The present work presents the author's experience in the implementation of tasks of Work package 2 "Intelligent security systems", Project BG05M2OP001-1.002-0006 Competence Center "Quantum Communi-

cation, Intelligent Security and Risk Management Systems (Quasar)", funded by the European Regional Development Fund through the Operational Programme "Science and education for smart growth", co-financed by the European Union through the European Structural and Investment Funds.

Business model for the development of physical security systems

Organizational strategy and competitiveness

There are many opportunities for BM configurations in the field of scientific research by adopting new technologies, discovering new user needs and promoting innovation through BM [1]. It follows from this that BM allows scientific organizations to become more competitive in the following areas, but not only: determination of their resources and activities, with the aim of turning them into a new synergy for the realization of applied scientific activity and market benefits; assisting the management to properly break down the action of the competitors. Comparing BMs competing in the same field of applied science paints a clear picture of the differences in how value is created and delivered; determination of profitable future arrangements and design of activities by applying strategic thinking in BM, incl. of key partnerships. In this sense, alternative BMs can be designed and compared, looking for competitiveness and sustainability. This process can contribute to increase the volume of knowledge, business and market decisions and develop perspective and BM presentation as an innovation, when scientific organizations present a novelty in the way they do business in the interest of the national business and economy. Such understanding and reinvention, in addition to continuous improvement, offers scientific organizations the sustainable competitive advantage needed to remain effective in an environment where the rules of the game are changing rapidly.

Business model

The main motivations underlying the development of the BM framework are related to the creation of a

technology and business platform for an Intelligent Security System (ISS) through which to present the research management (Picture 1) for ISS models developed in conditions of the QUASAR project.

Picture 1: BM framework for ISS development under the QUASAR project

After planning the activity, each component of the BM is designed for the management of research within the scope of the ISS under the QUASAR project:

Customer segment – the following likely interested parties for the development, construction and use of Intelligent Security Systems have been identified: users of security structures; users from departmental and local administrations; critical infrastructure operators; users from business organizations with a portfolio in the field of developing products and systems in the field of security and protection and users from academic and scientific organizations in the development of security and protection products and systems.

This component of BM, as one of the most important, is at the same time one of the most difficult to determine not only for products based on hardware and software, but also for those related to ensuring compatibility, including and interoperability, with strategic management systems established and operating at national level.

Value proposal – the main values of the products and systems (prices) perceived by the types of customers (Customer Segment) are obtained after conducting a study of market conditions, as well as taking into account the complexity of the products and systems.

Customer Relationship - using a website to present ISS models and their elements (sensor types, software, consulting system software, etc.). The ISS website may also offer an online chat for general support and resolution of inquiries and complaints. Another form of relationship building, especially with business clients, is participation in trade shows and technology conferences.

A concrete example is the ability to use the following web pages: <http://www.news-quasar.bg/>; <https://ims.bas.bg/departments/technologies-and-systems-for-protection/5defence-products-and-systems/>; <http://high-tech-ims.com/>.

Channels - it is possible to use different approaches to ensure the market realization of ISS, such as: partnership with national associations that include business organizations whose product list includes security and protection systems and the use of their markets; partnerships with business organizations from the EU; participation in projects of the European Commission (EC), the European Defence Agency (EDA) and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO), ensuring further development of technical and operational characteristics to the level of modern international requirements.

Key partners - when defining this component, the following opportunities were identified: suppliers of microelectronic elements, cloud services, etc.; partners on the QUASAR project - with proven capabilities in the field of risk assessment, a system for distributing aerial images in real time to users; simulations of risk events on land and water; providing secure communication (two-way), including quantum communication, etc.; business partners, national and international, with a portfolio in the field of security and protection systems; national agencies with responsibilities in the fields of security, defence, education and science, economy, regional development and public works and Patent Office of the Republic of Bulgaria.

Key activities - the scope of the identified key activities includes the following: hardware development: compatible with the security environment, light, secure, through minimal modifications, ensuring operation in different security environments; software development: intelligent software with capabilities for automated diagnostics (self-diagnosis) of sensor devices; Scenario software for the types of risk events (man-made or natural disasters), advisory system software, application support of the developed software; purchase of raw materials and electronic components, assembly, testing and packaging of products and systems; if necessary,

integration of the developed systems or their elements in the conditions of the business partners with whom there are agreements and distribution of the developed systems and products.

Key resources - during the development of this component, the focus was on: identification of the necessary human resources - software and hardware development teams; a team to integrate the elements of the ISS, as well as to the functioning strategic systems; advertising and communication team responsible for the promotion and distribution of the innovative product and identification of financial resources - financial means: determined by the QUASR project, ensuring the development of an ISS model, from the implementation of the tasks of the Plan for the scientific research activities of the Institute of Metal Science Equipment and Technologies with Hydro- and Aerodynamics Centre "Acad. A Balevski" at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, compatible with the activities of WP2, etc.

Cost structure - raw material costs, labor costs, cloud service and software provider costs, transportation and distribution costs, taxes and advertising costs. Other possible costs are related to hiring external consultants and specialists, as well as commission for sellers.

Revenue Streams - sources of income can be derived mainly from: the amount of ISS and sensor elements sold on the market (sales volume); participation in the process of development and integration of hardware and software in the working environment of a business organization/organization with which there is a contract; participation in the post-warranty maintenance of an ISS model implemented on the market, based on concluded contracts and participation in joint projects.

Generally, the BM framework can be defined as positive and useful, which also helps to consider approaches to develop new and/or optimize the characteristics of existing security systems as well as their elements. This applies to ISS models developed within WP2, as well as related software and hardware.

But BM, developed on the basis of established contemporary trends and good practices, is just the tip of the iceberg of things. In order to function properly, it is necessary to evaluate the vulnerability of the organization.

Organization's vulnerability

Definition

„vulnerability - weakness of an asset or control that can be exploited by one or more threats“ [2]

Organization's vulnerability

The concept of vulnerability, regarded as a global system property, includes three other concepts: degree of losses and damage; degree of exposure to danger and degree of stability.

In the context of current development, vulnerability is seen as a global technical property and is interpreted as a disadvantage or weakness in the design, development, operation and management of CI or its elements, which makes them susceptible to destruction or disability when exposed to danger or threat, or reduces the ability to recover under new stable conditions [3,4].

The goals of vulnerability analysis can be: identification of the likely events and a series of possible realization of those events that can cause damage and effects of loss to the planned goals; identification of the set of initiating events and an assessment of their cascading impact on a group of elements or on the CI, as a whole; identification of the set of events and/or series of those events that would cause damage and effects of loss in terms of planned goals and determination and development of dependencies and their connection in different sequences.

It is directly related to the assumed set of output events, probable sequences of events and expected observed outcomes.

The defined vulnerabilities of the key assets of the CIs are input information to formulate the requirements for the development of security systems and to determine the BM structure of the scientific organization developing these systems. In this regard, BM (Picture 1) was developed to build an ISS under QUASR project.

Conclusion

CI security has become a national and international priority. To be effective, vulnerability analyzes must be performed based on new, expanded paradigms. The high degree of connectivity (internal and external) that CIs achieve can make them vulnerable to global disruptions when exposed to hazards of various natures, from accidental mechanical/physical/material damage to natural events, software failures, intentional malicious impacts, human and organizational errors. This wider range of hazards and threats requires an all-hazards approach to understanding CI breach behavior to ensure their effective protection.

Considering the complexity of CIs, the determination of the characteristics of dangerous events and the assessment of their consequences and probabilities require an integrated framework capable of incorporating different analysis methods to capture the problem from different characteristic points of view related to their topology and properties - functional, logical and dynamic.

Therefore, a possible way to address this challenge is to conceptualize a control framework for CI vulnerability analysis and the relationship with BM in the development of security systems by scientific organizations, applying the multivariate approach to the occurrence of incidents that are beyond the design and operational safety restrictions of the CI (and its objects).

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